

Guidelines for Visual Communication of Probabilistic Information (PI)

ACCESSIBILITY Follow 508 Compliance Guidelines¹ but use this as first step to improve accessibility

LAYOUT Use the **template*** to ensure content **uniformity**. New templates should respect familiar design conventions (e.g. title at the top and supplemental information at the bottom). Organize thoughts with color blocking using a grid space approach like the example provided. Do not overcrowd the visual.

CONTENT

Title:	Explain the weather
Subtitle:	Set up Probabilistic Information (PI) visualization
PI Visualization:	Insert the PI visualization
Supplemental Info:	Explain the graphic and/or direct users to information about the source of the data or more specific forecast information. Keep it short!
Impact Statement:	<p><u>When</u> – Communicate the timing</p> <p><u>Potential Impacts</u> – Briefly describe the potential impacts</p> <p><u>What To Do</u> – Provide preventative guidance or action items aimed at reducing exposure to the potential impacts</p>

- COLOR**
- ✓ Use a single hue that varies in lightness to communicate uncertainty (darker = more certain)
 - ✓ Check colors with an online colorblindness simulator²
 - ⊘ Do not use red-green or orange-green color maps
 - ⊘ Do not use rainbow color maps
 - ⊘ Do not use colors that conflict with risk or hazard color scales

davidmathlogic.com/colorblind

FONT Arial, Univers, Helvetica
 Title 32 pt, subtitle 18 pt, body 16 pt, minimum size 14 pt
 Use **boldface** to draw attention and avoid italics

EMBELLISHMENT Communicate - don't decorate! Icons and photos should directly aid the message.

*Download the template: bit.ly/visualize_PI

1. section508.gov
 2. color-blindness.com/coblis-color-blindness-simulator